

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

FOLK PEDAGOGY ON THE PURPOSE, CONTENT AND MEANS OF MORAL EDUCATION OF CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL EDUCATIONAL NEEDS

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ABSTRACT

The article highlights the issue of the purpose, content and means of moral education in folk pedagogy. A theoretical analysis of scientific literature is provided.

Keywords: moral education, folk pedagogy, children's folklore.

Formulation of the problem . Preschool age is the most important period of human life, not preparation for future life, but real, bright, original, unique life. And the kind of person today's kid will become largely depends on what his childhood was like, what was the upbringing of a preschooler.

In order to revive the national spiritual and moral values lost in the past, it became necessary to turn to the folk roots, on which more than one generation of Ukrainians was raised, such as: Love (to God, people, Motherland), Faith, Hope, Honesty, Humanism, Respectful attitude towards people , Justice, Mercy. There is a noticeable interest in the pedagogical experience of the Ukrainian people, which is explained by many factors: the availability of folk-pedagogical content for the general public in society, in particular for preschoolers; its applied direction; harmony with the everyday spiritual needs and interests of parents and children; inexhaustible educational potential.

The purpose of the article: to analyze the content of folk pedagogy, its forms, methods and means, to identify the possibilities and ways of their use in the education and upbringing of children with special educational needs in the conditions of a modern preschool education institution.

Analysis of recent research and publications. H. Vashchenko considered the education of a person based on the principles of Christian morality and the spiritual achievements of the Ukrainian people. He concludes his textbook "Educational Ideal" with the words: "Fostering their best traditions, fighting for their independent state, Ukrainian youth must at the same time not only cherish universal ideals, but also actively fight for them" [1, 182] .

Presenting main material. In Ukraine, the term "children with special needs" is widely used, which is a literal translation of the English term "children-with special needs". In the minds of our society, the meaning of the term does not mean which, however, "needs" are important, which ones are "special" (or special), and which ones are not. At the same time, the concept of "special social needs" includes psychological and pedagogical aspects.

The term "individuals with special needs" was coined in the Declaration of Salamanca, which means that "special needs" apply to all individuals whose

needs lie in various physical or mental disabilities or difficulties, connected with the beginnings.

Particular light needs – this means the need for the minds necessary for the optimal implementation of current and potential abilities (physical, cognitive, mental, emotional-volitional, social etc.), which can This is to show a child with limited capabilities in the process of learning.

If we are talking about inclusive education, then the education of children with special educational needs, we are talking about a change in the basic principles of education, which in the first place can accommodate special educational needs.

In general, to address the special needs of children, a comprehensive psychological and pedagogical assessment of the development of a child is carried out - this is the process of collecting and interpreting complex and clear information about the peculiarities of the development of a child from met. It is tailored to specific lighting needs, including intelligence, and detailed recommendations for lighting programs, organization of the educational environment, the particularities of the organization of psychological and pedagogical, correctional and developmental services, including the potential capabilities of the child. A comprehensive psychological and pedagogical assessment of a child's development is carried out by faculties of inclusive resource centers and is the final result of the assessment process, which guides faculties of the IRC, teachers and fathers to determine optimal development This route is for children with special lighting needs.

The main tasks of a comprehensive psychological and pedagogical assessment of child development are:

- meeting special lighting needs;
- identification of the characteristics of the child's development, ii strong and weak sides;
- development of recommendations for the organization of provision of psychological-pedagogical, correctional and developmental services to children, as well as recommendations for educational programs for children, features of the organization of educational services, needs in Individual development programs;
- development of recommendations for organizing the educational process of children for the education administration, pedagogical workers, fathers or legal representatives of children.

The Law of Ukraine "On Lighting" indicates that those with special lighting needs will require additional steady and timely support in the lighting process in order to ensure the right to lighting, with Acceptance of development of specialness, improvement of health and quality of life, improvement of level of participation in life hawks. The reorientation of the educational process on a national basis led to the adoption of a number of documents that, at the theoretical level, shed light on this problem. Many scientists and practitioners are looking for the best option for pedagogical influence on the formation of a personality that would correspond to the ideal of a Ukrainian. We believe that the solution to this problem is possible taking into account the pedagogical experience of previous generations in the matter of training and education of the new generation.

For our research, the fundamental works of the prominent Ukrainian teacher M. Stelmakhovich are of great importance.

One of the main ones factors in the formation of personality is heredity. Long-term observations convince us that not only certain physical characteristics are inherited (it is not by chance that they say: *"the father was dug up"* or *"the mother was dug up"*, i.e. *"the same as the father"*, *"the same as the mother"*), natural predispositions of some abilities or properties, but also some character traits (*Like a potion, like a seed; Like a dam, like a mill: like a father, like a son; Like a bush, like a viburnum, like a mother, like a child*). However, most personality traits are not inherited, but acquired, in particular, in the process of education.

Folk pedagogy considers the environment - the state of relationships in the family - as the most important factor influencing the personality (*As the family has a harmonious life, so the child will grow up to the path; What is the treasure, when the family is in order; Father's and mother's prayer and with the sea throws out, and curses are drowned in puddles*), everyday life (*Whoever you deal with, that's what you get; Every bird sings its own song and has its own nest*), customs and traditions (*What is the land, then the custom, what is the side, then the news*), material condition (*Everyone likes his own corner; It will not be luxurious, but cozy; Good bedding and straw at home*), living conditions (*It is good to caress children there, where the stove is big and there is someone to cook*), social environment of the child (*The community is a big man*), etc.

Such a powerful factor in the formation of personality as education is clearly defined in popular ideas (*Not the parents who gave birth, but those who raised; A stone is polished, but a person is educated;*) All the named factors are considered by folk pedagogy as equally important, but in different situations each of them can become decisive [6, 38-39].

Retrospective analysis of the source base proves that the focus of Ukrainian folk pedagogy has always been the child, and folk pedagogy has never approved of childlessness, because *"a good father has a house full of children"*. The credo of folk pedagogy is eudaemonism: the natural right of every person to life, to the realization of their abilities, to happiness - to fate (*"It was my mother's will not to give those eyebrows. It was*

my mother's happiness to give my destiny!"). Thanks to the original pedagogical system, each nation reproduces and continues itself, its spiritual culture, life and production experience in children. All this, as well as many other factors, gives the full right to consider folk pedagogy as a leading source of development of a highly spiritual system of family and public education and pedagogical science, and with them, a national institution of preschool education and a democratic civil society, which our state is currently building.

Considering education as a process of preparing the younger generation for life, folk pedagogy placed moral education in the first place. This opinion is confirmed by a number of proverbs: *Someone else's soul is a dark forest; Pure morality is better than any necklace; Do not do to a friend what you do not like; Do not run ahead of people, and do not lag behind people; Be honest, don't praise yourself, don't insult others*, etc. Work, in turn, was considered as a means, as well as a method of moral education: *Work feeds a man; Work feeds, and laziness wastes; Work in grief is comforting; Happiness does not hide in the clouds, but is earned by hard work*, etc. That is why E. Syavavko stressed that "only a person who lives from his work can be highly moral in the popular sense. Only a hardworking person has all the other qualities of a highly moral person: honesty, truthfulness, sincerity" [7, 88.].

This opinion, by the way, is constantly confirmed in Ukrainian folklore. In numerous fairy tales about grandfather and grandmother's daughter ("Morozko", "About grandmother and grandfather's daughter", "Magic pipe", "Grandfather's daughter and the golden apple tree", "The golden shoe") it is shown how due to laziness and unwillingness to work, grandmother's daughter succeeds to tricks, deception. Actually, folklore examples, Ye. Ilyin claims, "motivated me to raise and solve the topic of work as a moral one in all literature lessons, because "the soul is obliged to work" [3, 43].

According to the traditions of folk pedagogy, a child should learn the first moral norms in the family. It was here that children were taught from the youngest age: respect the elder, give him primacy in everything, respect old age, do not neglect the advice of the elders. Ethnographers note a kind of subordination in the life of large families. So, when everyone sat down at the table and ate from the same bowl, the oldest member of the family was the first to pick the dish, then everyone else, giving priority to the oldest. When one of the children tried to break this rule, he was punished immediately at the table (an older child hit him on the head with a spoon). Ukrainians usually call father, mother, older family members and generally older people by "Vy". Children should politely greet elders, bow when meeting, and boys should remove their headgear. This way of life had a huge positive impact on the formation of children's morality. As E. Syavavko notes, in such conditions "the child gets used to the idea that in society the one whose participation in socially useful work is greater, who can do more for others, who has more experience, receives a greater reward" [7, 87]. It is precisely this feature of folk pedagogy that should be paid more attention in modern

education, in particular, of older preschoolers, because nowadays children get all the best, and that in the first place. This, unfortunately, develops children's selfishness, which sometimes has undesirable consequences at an older age.

Moral education of younger generations is carried out by folk pedagogy with the help of certain means, which, according to M. Stelmakhovich, "should be understood as the type of activity, phenomenon or object that can influence the personality in a certain direction" [6, 50].

According to V. Mosiyashenka, the leading means of folk pedagogy are: "native language, oral folk art, national mythology and symbolism, folk art, national traditions, customs and rites, folk games, toys, rituals and celebrations, direct personal work, nature, a lullaby, skits, stories, fairy tales, ditties, consolations, jokes, invocations, the atmosphere of a native Mivka, the example of elders, children's amateur activities, folk aphorisms, proverbs, sayings" [4, 15]. In these means, national morality and norms of coexistence are embodied, following which and passing them down from generation to generation, Ukrainians developed in themselves the traits of national character, national character, which served as the basis of their life activities throughout the ages.

Among the above-mentioned means, oral folk art, in particular children's folklore, is characterized by an extremely large educational and developmental potential. "Traditional children's folklore," - notes G. Dovzhenok, "like no other part of folk creativity, had a clearly demonstrated practical meaning, forming an integral part of practical folk pedagogy." He contributed to the implementation of the main functions of education as a whole: care for the physical and moral health of the younger generation, development of mental abilities and preparation for useful activities of young members, working groups of society" [2, 4].

The purpose of using folklore is to enrich the speech of preschoolers, to prepare them for a better perception of artistic works, to expand the range of their interests, to attract the younger generation to the origins of folk traditions, to form the ability to learn, to create conditions for a conscious choice of a future profession and life path, neglect the spiritual world of a young person.

The modern stage of folklore development is characterized by such main features as pronounced regional affiliation and historical concreteness; close relationship with history; originality and relevance; high educational potential.

Taking into account the above-mentioned features of folklore, we have reason to say that it is their significance that prompts teachers to make practical use of the inexhaustible wealth of oral folk creativity in the modern educational process. Today, the artistic value of folk poetic works is recognized by many scientists, the educational value of any folklore genre has long been appreciated by outstanding teachers of the past and leading methodologists of the present, which is confirmed by their inclusion in books for reading, use in preschool practice, and children's leisure time.

Particularly high educational potential is characteristic of lullabies, nursery rhymes, tongue twisters, counters, riddles, the theme of which is the unity of man with nature, the wish for a child to grow up to be a good person, a beautiful craftswoman, to live in work and find happiness in the family.

Research by N. Sivachuk confirms that the lullaby can be called "the first encyclopedia of Ukrainian studies, because it introduces the child to the world of the native ethnic group, its language, religion, history, culture, morals, customs, through it the child gets the first ideas about national ideals, about good and evil" [5, 53], about what is "possible" and "impossible". According to the researchers, special informativeness about the moral laws of Ukrainian society is contained in lullabies, in which many episodes are associated with animals close to the child (the image of a bull, a mouse, a bee, a kitten, a purring cat, a gray cat), through the assessment of whose actions, instruction is expressed.

Satire and humor occupy a large place in Ukrainian folk art. We already meet humorous works in children's folklore. Such is the song "Crane", which has no end, because it repeats the same thing with which it began; a song about the "White-sided Magpie", which cooked and gave porridge to the children, but did not give porridge to the lazy and careless shirtless man, etc.

In children's folklore, such a genre as fairy tales, in which implausible stories are told, has become widespread, and this strengthens children's understanding of what can be real in life, and what is invented. Let us cite, for example, one of these fables: "I went to shake pears on the willows. I shook it, caught crucians, took it to the bazaar, sold a dozen of honey, recruited a retinue, sewed boots and still wear them." In our opinion, it contributes to the formation of truthfulness and sincerity in preschoolers.

Ukrainian proverbs and sayings figuratively express the basic principles and norms of the people's life ("It is good to live where one sows and plows in a group", "It is better to do good than to say good", etc.), therefore they are called the national moral code. In addition, they have accumulated high wisdom of the people (conclusions from observations, moral assessment of actions and deeds, encouragement of good and punishment of evil). Unlike other types of oral folk art, proverbs and sayings are as often as possible related to everyday life, accessible to the widest strata and do not require special circumstances and a wide audience. It is not for nothing that the name itself indicates that proverbs are used "on the word", on occasion, that is, when it is necessary to emphasize, underline, highlight the main idea from everything said before and always have a practical meaning, serve as ready-made formulas and rules, the ultimate goal which are education of appropriate actions and actions of a person, his character. This genre serves as a kind of code of moral behavior, in which you can find advice, support, and condemnation ("You like to ride, you also like to drive sleds"; "A full ear of corn bends to the ground, and an empty one fights against it"; "A bee stings with its sting, and a person - in a word").

Let us emphasize that in folk pedagogy there were no educational means far from real life, and therefore

the requirements set forth in proverbs for the spiritual and physical state of the individual expressed the ideal of moral education, its ultimate goal. Actually, this is what gives grounds for their most active use as a means of moral education of children ("*Pure morality is better than any necklace*").

Undoubtedly, a fairy tale is the most wonderful thing that has the opportunity to operate with a great educational potential in the moral direction of a young listener or reader. As a rule, a certain moral idea is embedded in a fairy tale - the condemnation of evil, the victory of good, the glorification of work, justice, and bravery. In addition, the establishment of moral laws of life is its main idea. Moral norms and principles, ethical and aesthetic ideals of the people are vividly expressed in it.

V. Sukhomlynskyi theoretically substantiated and confirmed in practice that "a fairy tale is inseparable from beauty, it promotes the development of aesthetic feelings, without which the nobility of the soul, heartfelt sensitivity to human misfortune, grief, and suffering are unthinkable. Thanks to the fairy tale, the child gets to know the world not only with his mind, but also with his heart" [7, 43]. In his opinion, a fairy tale is a beneficial and irreplaceable source of fostering love for the Motherland. The educational potential of the fairy tale is determined by its rich language: it is singing, poetic, full of metaphors and similes, proverbs and sayings, very apt and instructive. All this makes the fairy tale an effective means of raising and teaching children of different ages, including children with special educational needs. A notable feature of a fairy tale is that it can depict the surrounding world of people, their actions and destinies in an exciting way and with accessible artistic means, as well as show in a short time what

this or that action of the hero leads to, gives an opportunity for 15- 20 minutes to try on yourself and experience someone else's fate, other people's feelings, joy and sorrow. This is a unique opportunity to perceive, "lose" life situations without harming one's own health and fate, putting the fairy tale on a par with the most effective means of educational work with older preschoolers

Conclusions. Further prospects for solving the problems of moral education, as evidenced by the analysis, require the search for new, most effective ways or rethinking of already known and most effective folk-pedagogical means.

References

1. Vashchenko G. Educational ideal: A textbook for teachers, pupils, youth and parents. - Poltava: Poltava Herald, 1994. - 192 p.
2. Dovzhenok G.V. Ukrainian children's folklore. - K.: Scientific Thought, 1981. - 171 p.
3. Mosiyashenko V.A. Ukrainian ethnopedagogy: Study guide. - Sumy: VTD "University book", 2005. - 176 p.
4. Sivachuk N. The educational potential of Ukrainian folk lullabies // Elementary school. – 2006. - #1. - P.51-55.
5. Stelmakhovich M.G. Ukrainian folk pedagogy. - K.: IZYN, 1997. - 232 p.
6. Stupak Yu.P. Educational significance of Ukrainian folklore. - Kyiv, 1960. - 30 p.
7. Syavavko E.I. Ukrainian ethnopedagogy: Educational and methodological manual. – Lviv: Publishing Center of LNU named after I. Frank. - 2002. - 159p.